

Second crop rice in Rajasthan

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Nearly 2,000 ha of ricefields in zone IVb of Rajasthan remain waterlogged during the dry season. Because of the tank bed nature, it is not possible to raise wheat or other crops. The zone is characterized by mild, short winters with comparatively high humidity.

We explored raising a rice crop or a ratoon crop during off-season.

Seeds of 10 rice varieties with different growth durations (110-150 d) were sown at 20-d intervals from the first week of Dec 1985 to the second week of Jan 1986. Seedlings were transplanted at the 4-5 leaf stage at 15 × 15-cm spacing under high fertility. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Seedling growth in the dry season was slower than in the wet season. It took 2 to 2-1/2 mo to attain the 4-5 leaf stage in all varieties. In the first sowing, plant height ranged from 60 to 85 cm, with 13-37 panicle-bearing tillers. Panicle length ranged from 17.2 to 24 cm. In the second sowing, plant height increased significantly, ranging from 69 to 95.1 cm with 27-47 panicle-bearing tillers. Panicle length also increased significantly. In the last sowing, all the three ancillary characters were drastically reduced.

Short-duration varieties matured 56-78 d after transplanting; medium-duration varieties took an average 90 d to mature (Table 1). Yields were relatively high when seeds were sown in the third week of Dec (more productive tillers and better panicle length). Pusa 2-21, IET7566, and BK79 yielded significantly better than the other varieties.

The ratooning ability of the 10 varieties sown on 25 Dec 1985 was assessed. The main crop was harvested the first week of May 1986. Plants were cut 8 cm from ground level and allowed to ratoon. Fertilizer at 40 kg N and 40 kg P/ha was applied basally just after the main crop harvest; 40 kg N/ha

Table 1. Average yield of rice varieties in off-season. Banswara, India, 1985-86.

Variety	Sowing 1		Sowing 2		Sowing 3		Av yield (t/ha)
	Days to maturity	Yield (t/ha)	Days to maturity	Yield (t/ha)	Days to maturity	Yield (t/ha)	
BK190	88	2.0	92	2.0	122	0.6	1.5
BK398	81	1.7	85	1.6	114	0.4	1.3
Chambal	80	0.4	87	2.4	112	0.7	1.2
Ratna	70	0.4	78	1.9	109	0.4	0.7
BK79	73	3.0	76	2.4	108	1.5	2.3
IET7566	63	1.0	65	4.0	95	1.5	2.2
Pusa 2-21	62	3.2	69	5.2	102	1.2	3.2
BK664	64	1.5	74	2.5	106	1.9	2.0
BK665	77	1.5	73	0.4	105	0.9	0.9
Av		1.5		2.3		0.9	
LSD (0.05)		0.9		1.3		0.5	
CV		15.4		7.3		9.7	

Table 2. Performance of ratoon crops of rice varieties. Banswara, India, 1985-86.

Variety	Ratoon crop						Main crop		
	Days to flowering	Days to maturity	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle-bearing tillers (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Av yield (t/ha)	Days to flowering	Days to maturity	Av yield (t/ha)
BK190	57	75	81.1	14	20.8	4.0	112	145	7.0
BK398	49	70	75.1	11	21.5	2.5	110	140	5.8
BK79	50	68	56.9	22	19.1	2.1	102	140	6.0
BK664	49	66	55.6	14	17.1	1.7	90	123	5.5
BK665	49	67	58.7	13	18.4	2.3	93	125	5.5
IET7564	46	62	69.5	19	18.6	1.2	88	110	3.5
IET7566	50	65	71.8	15	21.3	1.0	80	109	4.0
Pusa 2-21	50	66	51.6	15	17.2	1.5	78	107	4.5
Ratna	59	68	56.4	20	19.5	1.6	78	108	4.2
Chambal	50	71	56.3	19	17.9	3.2	85	105	3.0
LSD (0.05) = 0.4 t/ha									
CV = 9.8%									

was applied 1 mo after main crop harvest.

Highest grain yield (4 t/ha) was from BK 190, followed by Chambal (3.2 t/ha)

and BK398 (2.5 t/ha) (Table 2). All the medium-duration varieties had better ratooning ability; short-duration varieties had poor ability. □

Fish production from rainfed ricefields in northeast Thailand

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We interviewed 20 farmers participating in a CARE rice - fish culture project in Yasothorn Province weekly during the 1986 rainy season to compare stocked fingerling and wild fish production.

No trenches were dug; catch ponds doubled as fish refuges. Farmers grew

photoperiod-sensitive, long-stalked rice varieties such as Dok Mali 105 (ordinary rice) and San Pa Thong (glutinous). Transplanting was completed in late Jun. Fertilizer and manure application varied widely (av 100 kg N/ha). Pesticide (methyl parathion) was sometimes used for crab control before transplanting, but did not cause problems. Harvest was around 20 Nov, averaging 1.5-2 t rice/ha.

Fingerlings (34 cm; US\$1/100 fish) of *C. carpio*, *O. niloticus*, and *P. gonionotus* were stocked 2 Jul at a 2:1:1 ratio. Recommended stocking rate was